
Are Google and Bing Featured Snippets more accurate than chatbots?

A number of this blog's posts were selected as Featured Snippets by Google and Bing, and they typically offered accurate answers to the queries. Will chatbot search engines be as good?

The AI chatbot wars

The emergence of [ChatGPT](#) and the intense chatbot competition between OpenAI / Microsoft vs. Google rekindled my curiosity about search engines. Just this week, Forbes announced that the "[ChatGPT Wars Erupt as Google and Microsoft Race to Market](#)." A few days later, [The Wall Street Journal reported that the "AI war heats up"](#) as Google announced that it will launch a ChatGPT competitor within weeks. And today, [Microsoft integrated OpenAI ChatGPT into its search engines Bing and Edge](#), with the Bing homepage now enabling users to follow up on their queries with a ChatGPT.

[Microsoft new AI-improved Bing and Edge browsers are described more powerful than ChatGPT. But are they more accurate?](#)

With the widespread popularity of ChatGPT and its imminent integration into Microsoft's search engines, Google freaked out. The trillion dollar company [issued a code red](#) and [brought back its co-founders Larry Page and Sergey Brin to fight back](#). There is so

much at play. [We make about 100,000 Google searches per second](#) that [add up to more than 8.5 billion searches a day](#). The search engine industry takes [\\$120 billion in revenues](#) and [Google's hold on this industry is remarkable with a 93% market share](#).

[Search engine market share worldwide via StatCounter.](#)

Will chatbot powered search engines hallucinate as badly as ChatGPT?

These chatbot “wars” will be fascinating to follow. But users, notably academics and scientists, have reasons to be concerned. Despite all of its amazing prowesses, ChatGPT is known to [hallucinate](#), namely to provide articulate and confident answers that peddle nonsense. Will AI-powered search engines hallucinate as badly as ChatGPT?

The point of chatbots is to produce synthetic answers gathered from multiple sources. So far, such answers aren’t supported by links and references as expected in academic writing or even in a typical Google or Bing search page. Synthetic answers are prone to make stuff up as you will see below.

What are Featured Snippets?

A precursor to search engine chatbots are [Feature Snippets](#), the excerpts of texts highlighted at the top of Google or Bing search pages. [Feature Snippets](#), as Google calls them, can be text quotes, lists or tables, that are extracted from web pages that are indexed by the search engine. They provide a snapshot answer to the search query.

Below is an example Featured Snippet. In contrast to chatbots like ChatGPT, the answer is associated with a reference web page (hopefully a reliable source) and the link to the web

page is provided enabling users to quickly follow up, check the source and gather more information.

About 13,800,000 results (0.41 seconds)

Featured snippets are **special boxes where the format of a regular search result is reversed, showing the descriptive snippet first**. They can also appear within a related questions group (also known as "People Also Ask"). Read more about how Google's Featured Snippets work.

<https://developers.google.com> › ... › Documentation

Featured Snippets and Your Website | Google Search Central

Featured Snippets are known as “Position #0” because they appear above the #1 spot on a Google search page. In their support pages, [Google explains how Featured Snippets are chosen from web search listings](#):

“Google’s automated systems determine whether a page would make a good featured snippet to highlight for a specific search request. Your feedback helps us improve our search algorithms and the quality of your search results.”

Feature Snippets from this blog generally feature accurate answers

I was pleasantly surprised that excerpts of a number of posts from this blog got picked up as Featured Snippets. I didn’t make any particular effort to enable this and I only recently became familiar with the Snippets. Good to know that you don’t need hire an SEO (Search Engine Optimization) expert to be featured.

Parenthetically, SEO is a fast growing industry of its own [with a market size of \\$50 billion](#). Given the value of having your company or product pop up high on a Google search page, an entire industry of experts and consultants guide web designers in optimizing their pages to show up high on search pages. Feature Snippets can also be coveted although some argue that having the answer right on the search page discourages clicking in the links and racking up valuable income through page visits. In any case, the SEO industry is about to be shaken up to its core given the disruption that chatbots will bring to our internet searching habits.

Let’s review 5 posts from this blog that got picked up by Google or Bing as Featured Snippets. They tend to provide accurate answers to the query along with a link to original source. That’s good news compared to the tendency of ChatGPT to make stuff up leaving me generally baffled as I can’t trace back the statements to a specific source.

These are the 5 articles that have Featured Snippets:

[What's a failed experiment?](#)

This popular article on how to deal with negative results in the lab was titled as a question, and Google did dig out the answer even though it was buried deep in the text.

Google's main competitor, [Microsoft's own search engine Bing](#), also picked up the exact same quote. Bing has its own version of the Featured Snippets. This was one of Google's Featured Snippet from this blog that was also highlighted by Bing.

Welcome to the new Bing

Your AI-powered answer engine

Ask anything

A failed experiment is **one that was poorly executed, poorly controlled or simply failed on technical grounds.** If an experiment is well-controlled and conducted to the best of current knowledge, techniques, and research abilities, then it's not strictly speaking failed.

FAILED EXPERIMENT

[What's a failed experiment? - Medium](#)

kamounlab.medium.com/whats-a-failed-experiment-7ea66fd96f8

What are some examples?

How to learn from them?

How to avoid them?

Type a message...

As you can see in the screenshots, Bing has already integrated a chatbot feature to the Snippet. The “New Bing” include an “AI-powered answer engine.” As far as I can tell, the new Bing chat mode isn’t widely available yet, but if you’re anxious to use it you can join a waiting list. [You can find out more about the new Bing here.](#) It sounds very much like ChatGPT. Let’s hope it will not make up stuff as much as the other chatbots.

Chat mode is only available when you have access to the new Bing.

I need to throw a dinner party for 6 people who don't eat nuts or seafood. Can you suggest a 3-course menu?

- ✓ Search the web for: **3 course menu no nuts no seafood**
- ✓ Search the web for: **course menu examples**

A possible 3-course menu for 6 people who don't like nuts or seafood is:

- **Starter:** Vegetable soup with gluten-free bread. Warm and healthy dish with various veggies and herbs.
- **Main:** Roasted chicken with roasted potatoes and green beans. Classic and satisfying dish with garlic, lemon, and rosemary.
- **Dessert:** Apple crisp with vanilla ice cream. Delicious and nut-free dessert with cinnamon and gluten-free crumble.

I have sweet potato already. Can you make the main course use that?

Sure, you can use sweet potato in your main course. Here is one possible option:

- **Sweet potato and spinach lasagna.** This is a vegetarian and gluten-free dish that layers sweet potato slices, spinach, ricotta cheese, and tomato sauce in a baking dish.

Introducing the new Bing, your AI-powered answer engine

Join the waitlist

Learn more

What is GOHREP?

GOHREP is a framework developed to help researchers design and plan their experiments. The acronym stands for Goal, Hypothesis, Rationale, Experimental Plan. If you ask about, both Google and Bing will display the answer.

A screenshot of a Google search page. The search bar contains the text "explain gohrep". Below the search bar, there are navigation tabs for "All", "Images", "Videos", "News", "Shopping", and "More". The search results show "About 1,580 results (0.37 seconds)". A red text prompt says "Did you mean: explain *goprep*". Below that, a snippet of text reads: "What is GOHREP? It stands for **GOal, Hypothesis, Rationale, Experimental Plan**. GOal — here you write your main objective; what do you want to achieve in the project; achieving this goal is what defines the success of the project. 24 Oct 2021". A link is shown: "https://kamounlab.medium.com › gohrep-and-plesi-guide...". The link text is "GOHREP and PLESI: guides to navigate through your ...". At the bottom right of the search results, there are links for "About featured snippets" and "Feedback".

A screenshot of a Microsoft Bing search page. The search bar contains the text "what is gohrep". Below the search bar, there are navigation tabs for "ALL", "SHOPPING", "IMAGES", "VIDEOS", "MAPS", "CHAT", and "MORE". The search results show "About 9,730,000 results" and a "Date" dropdown. On the left side, there is a blue box with the text "Welcome to the new Bing" and "Your AI-powered answer engine", with a button that says "Ask anything". The main search result is a large white box with the title "GOal, Hypothesis, Rationale, Experimental Plan". Below the title, there is a snippet of text: "What is GOHREP? It stands for **GOal, Hypothesis, Rationale, Experimental Plan**. GOal — here you write your main objective; what do you want to achieve in the project; achieving this goal is what...". Below that, there is a link: "GOHREP and PLESI: guides to navigate through your research ...". At the bottom of the link, there is a URL: "kamounlab.medium.com/gohrep-and-plesi-guides-to-navigate-through-your-i".

Tips for writing paper Twitter threads?

This post discusses and lists tips for writing Twitter threads of academic papers. Google displays it as Featured Snippets, but if you ask for a list of tips you only get a mash-up of the bulleted list.

explain paper twitter threads

All Images News Books Shopping More

Tools

About 18,700,000 results (0.43 seconds)

The paper thread is **a narrative about your paper posted on social media, typically Twitter**. It's one example of recent efforts to communicate science in a more spontaneous manner beyond the outdated rigid norms of academic writing.

<https://kamounlab.medium.com/tips-for-writing-academ...>

[Tips for writing academic paper threads | by KamounLab](#)

About featured snippets Feedback

list tips for writing paper threads

All Images Shopping Videos Books More

Tools

About 47,300,000 results (0.76 seconds)

Tips for writing paper threads

The best threads go through a classic story narrative, perhaps not as dramatic as these, but a story nonetheless. Avoid being too wordy. Shorter is better. Link to the paper in the first tweet so interested readers can easily navigate to it.

<https://kamounlab.medium.com/tips-for-writing-academ...>

[Tips for writing academic paper threads | by KamounLab](#)

About featured snippets Feedback

[How to select a PhD lab?](#)

There are several versions of this article. Google displays a list from [the oldest version from my Tumblr blog](#). But if you ask for a list of tips then Google will display the list from the version of the article published in the Royal Society publication *The Biologist* "[11 tips for choosing the right PhD.](#)"

how to select phd lab

[All](#) [Videos](#) [Images](#) [News](#) [Books](#) [More](#)

[Tools](#)

About 47,800,000 results (0.47 seconds)

How to select a PhD lab?

1. Build a network of mentors and colleagues who can candidly advise you. ...
2. Identify a general topic that inspires you. ...
3. Pick a topic that keeps you up at night and makes you dream. ...
4. Do not get too specific with the research topic. ...
5. Once you identify a lab you like, do your homework.

[More items...](#)

<https://kamounlab.tumblr.com/post/how-to-select-a-ph...>

[How to select a PhD lab? - Kamoun Lab @ TSL](#)

[About featured snippets](#) • [Feedback](#)

tips choosing phd lab

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[Tools](#)

About 22,000,000 results (0.51 seconds)

11 tips for choosing the right PhD

1. Use networking to help with your decision. ...
2. Identify a general topic that inspires you. ...
3. Consider internships or work experience first. ...
4. Have some flexibility. ...
5. Do your research. ...
6. Pay them a visit. ...
7. Reputations matter. ...
8. Don't just follow the glamour or the money.

[More items...](#) • 30 Nov 2021

<https://www.rsb.org.uk/biologist-opinion/11-tips-for-c...>

[11 tips for choosing the right PhD - Royal Society of Biology](#)

[About featured snippets](#) • [Feedback](#)

[What are NLR networks?](#)

How about science posts? These do get picked up too. If you ask Google to explain NLR networks (these are immune receptor proteins), then it picks up a medium post on the topic.

Bing, on the other hand, prefers to top the page with [the article by my collaborators Jiorgos Kourelis and Hiroaki Adachi](#). Damn' 🙄🙄

Google search results for "explain nlr networks". The search bar shows the query and the Google logo. Below the search bar are navigation tabs for All, Images, News, Videos, Books, and More. The results show approximately 1,880,000 results in 0.44 seconds. A featured snippet is displayed, titled "NLRs are multi-domain proteins. They have a central domain, the NB-ARC domain, which acts as a switch: NLR proteins get switched on through conformational changes resulting from an ADP to ATP switch in this nucleotide-binding domain. Plant NLR proteins have additional domains, including a variable N-terminal domain." The snippet is dated 17 Sept 2021 and includes a link to [https://kamounlab.medium.com/nlr-receptor-networks-filling-the-gap-between-evolutionary ...](https://kamounlab.medium.com/nlr-receptor-networks-filling-the-gap-between-evolutionary-and-...). There are also links for "About featured snippets" and "Feedback".

Microsoft Bing search results for "explain nlr networks". The search bar shows the query and the Microsoft Bing logo. Below the search bar are navigation tabs for ALL, IMAGES, VIDEOS, MAPS, NEWS, CHAT, and MORE. The results show approximately 4,590,000 results. A featured snippet is displayed, titled "Activation and Regulation of NLR Immune Receptor ...". The snippet includes a link to <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35941738> and a brief description: "In this review, we highlight the concept of NLR networks, discussing how they are formed, activated, and regulated. Two main types of NLR networks have been described in plants: the ADR1/NRG1 network and the NRC network. In both networks, multiple helper NLRs function as signalling hubs for sensor NLRs and cell surface-localized immune receptors." Below the snippet are links for "feedback" and "thumbs up/down". Another result is shown below, titled "NLR receptor networks: filling the gap between evolutionary and ...", with a link to [https://kamounlab.medium.com/nlr-receptor-networks-filling-the-gap-between...](https://kamounlab.medium.com/nlr-receptor-networks-filling-the-gap-between-...). A date and snippet are also visible: "Web 13 Sep 2021 · Pathogen effectors that suppress helper NLR hubs in the NRC network. What Lida found then is these two effectors AVRcap1b from Phytophthora infestan..."

How do Featured Snippets compare to ChatGPT?

I queried Google and ChatGPT with a highly specialized science question related to a protein sequence motif we call MADA that is present at the N-terminus of NLR immune receptors. This is what happened.

what is mada motif

All

Images

Videos

Shopping

News

More

Tools

About 3,320,000 results (0.31 seconds)

The MADA motif **matches the N-terminal α 1 helix of Arabidopsis NLR protein ZAR1, which undergoes a conformational switch during resistosome activation.**

Immunoassays revealed that the MADA motif is functionally conserved across NLRs from distantly related plant species. 27 Nov 2019

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov> > ...

[An N-terminal motif in NLR immune receptors is ... - PubMed](#)

About featured snippets • Feedback

Google Featured Snippet gave an accurate answer extracted from an original scientific article gathered from PubMed, the highly curated biological literature database. In contrast, this is what ChatGPT produced:

so what is mada motif

The MADA motif is a sequence of amino acids commonly found in proteins that is believed to play a role in regulating their structure and function. The MADA acronym stands for "Multiply And Diversely Aligned." This motif is of interest to scientists due to its association with a variety of cellular processes, such as protein-protein interactions, protein folding, and signaling. Understanding the MADA motif can provide insights into how proteins work, which may have implications for developing new drugs and treatments for diseases.

ChatGPT hallucinated. As far as I can tell, this answer is gibberish. Worse, I can't trace the false statements back to a source. A Google search for "Multiply And Diversely Aligned" yielded absolutely nothing informative. I still can't tell if this is a made up acronym.

In an earlier chat with a similar query, ChatGPT came up with more nonsense that could easily confuse a naive reader. It wrote:

"The MADA motif is the sequence "MVDA", which appears in the first four amino acids of the protein. The MADA motif is a signature sequence found in a group of plant effector proteins called "molecules against DEfence". These proteins are secreted by plant pathogens and are thought to play a role in overcoming the plant's defense mechanisms during infection."

Will AI-powered search engines be more accurate than ChatGPT?

In the article "[Talking About Large Language Models](#)," Murray Shanahan delineates the limits of chatbots trained using Large Language Models and explores the philosophical implications of mimicking human language. [John Naughton, Professor of the public understanding of technology, explains this further in The Guardian](#):

"...if you give the model a prompt such as "The first person to walk on the moon was ... " and it responds with "Neil Armstrong", that's not because the model knows anything about the moon or the Apollo mission but because we are actually asking it the following question: "Given the statistical distribution of words in the vast public corpus of [English] text, what words are most likely to follow the sequence 'The first person to walk on the moon was'? A good reply to this question is 'Neil Armstrong'."

ChatGPT turned out to be a remarkable virtual assistant that performs incredibly well at many tasks, but correctly answering knowledge queries isn't one of them. We will soon find out whether the chatbot apps integrated into Bing and Google perform better at this task.

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